

Questionnaire for

THE ASSESSMENT OF THE POTENTIAL SOCIAL IMPACTS

RELATED TO THE SEAWEED HARVESTING AND PROCESSING

PROCEDURES.

1. INTRODUCTION

We would like to ask for your cooperation in filling out the following questionnaire.

The goal is to acquire opinions and information about potential social impacts on stakeholders that can be directly involved in the seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation and seaweed refining sector.

The S-LCA aims to assess social consequences (positive or negative) on different stakeholder categories:

Workers

Local
community

Consumers

Value chain
actors

2. THE QUESTIONNAIRE FOR “WORKERS” STAKEHOLDERS

Social indicator: Health and Safety

Q1. Could the workers of the processes listed below be exposed to risks of accidents/damages to human health, assuming complete compliance with all the health and safety standards and laws?				
Processes	YES	If YES, which kind of risk (high, medium, low)? You can also describe it.	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

Q2. Could the workers of the processes listed below carry out strenuous activities?				
Processes	YES	If YES, which kind of risk (high, medium, low)? You can also describe it.	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

Social indicator: Working hours

Q3. Could the workers of the processes listed below exceed the 40-48 hours worked per week?				
Processes	YES	If YES, which kind of risk: - High (>50% of workers exceed) - Medium (<50% of workers exceed)	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

Social indicator: Social benefits/social security

Considering this list of social benefits:

- Medical insurance
- Dental Insurance
- Paramedical insurance (i.e., preventive medicine)
- Medicine Insurance
- Wage insurance
- Paid maternity and paternity leave
- Paid sick leave
- Education and training
- Meal voucher
- Agreement with gyms, kindergartens, etc.
- Others

Q4. Do the workers involved in the processes listed below have access to the majority of these social benefits as part of their employment perks?				
Processes	YES, If they can obtain more than 6 social benefits. If you select others, please specify	NO	If NO, which kind of risk level: - High (no social benefits) - Medium (1-2 social benefits) - Low (2-6 social benefits)	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

3. THE QUESTIONNAIRE FOR “LOCAL COMMUNITY” STAKEHOLDERS

Social indicator: Safe and healthy living conditions

Q5. Could the presence of the processes listed below increase the perception of a higher risk of affecting the living conditions of local communities? For example, due to occasional events such as accidents or exposure to emissions in the environmental matrices.				
Processes	YES	If YES, which kind of risk level (High, medium, low)? You can also describe it.	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

Social indicator: Local economic development

Q6. Could the presence of the processes listed below contribute positively to the development of the local economy?				
Processes	YES	If YES, could you explain how?	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

Q7. Could the presence of the processes listed below contribute positively to the employment of local workers?				
Processes	YES.	NO or only to a rather extent	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

Q8. Could the presence of the processes listed below enhance the activity of local suppliers (e.g., for providing materials, components, or services)?				
Processes	YES	NO or only to a rather extent	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

Q9. Could the presence of the processes listed below enhance the development of local "satellite activities"?				
Processes	YES	If YES, which kind of activity	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

4. THE QUESTIONNAIRE FOR "CONSUMER" STAKEHOLDERS

Social indicator: Health and safety

Q10. Are the processes listed below considering the health and safety of the consumers?				
Processes	YES	If YES, which kind of activity (i.e., the presence of specific management measures, labels of health and safety requirements, an adaptation of ISO 9001 standard, etc....)	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

Social indicator: Transparency

Q11. Are the processes listed below targeting transparency for the consumers?				
Processes	YES	If YES, which kind of activity (i.e., certification standards, environmental labels, special indices, sustainability reports)	NO	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation				
Seaweed processing				

5. THE QUESTIONNAIRE FOR “VALUE CHAIN” STAKEHOLDERS

Social indicator: Fair competition*

Q12. Are the “actors” involved in the processes listed below contributing to fair competition among the other stakeholders in the value chain?			
Processes	YES	If YES, what kind of activity and to what extent (highly, positively, low, very low) do they contribute?	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation			
Seaweed processing			

* Fair competition regards anti-competitive behavior: actions of the reporting “actor” that may result in collusion with potential competitors to fix prices, coordinate bids, create market or output restrictions, impose geographic quotas, or allocate customers, suppliers, geographic areas, and product lines with the purpose of limiting the effects of market competition.

Social indicator: Promoting social responsibility*

Q13. Are the “actors” involved in the processes listed below promoting social responsibility among its suppliers and through their own actions?			
Processes	YES	If YES, what kind of activity and to what extent (highly, positively, low, very low) do they contribute?	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation			
Seaweed processing			

* Social responsibility is an “actor’s” obligation to consider the interests of its stakeholders as customers, employees, shareholders, or consumers. This indicator can be evaluated by considering if the “actor” manages its suppliers in a socially responsible way, including monitoring, auditing, and training efforts. And the possibility of taking action toward suppliers when warranted.

Social indicator: Wealth distribution*

Q14. Are the “actors” involved in the processes listed below promoting wealth distribution in the supply chain? Some examples could be contract instruments, interbranch organization, and the definition of a fair price for the products.			
Processes	YES	If YES, what kind of activity and to what extent (highly, positively, low, very low) do they contribute?	I DO NOT KNOW (I have not appropriate info and/or data)
Seaweed harvesting/collection/cultivation			
Seaweed processing			

* Wealth distribution focuses on how the value is distributed among all the actors of the value chain. An equal distribution is obtained when a fair selling price for a product or service is established, i.e., when the price is such that it covers all the production costs and everyone returns an acceptable profit margin.

Name and Surname of the member of the panel of experts:

Affiliation:

Date: